

STUDIES ON THE RELATION BETWEEN CHEMICAL CONSTITUTION AND
ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF OPTICALLY ACTIVE
AND RACEMIC COMPOUNDS. PART V. CORRELATION OF
ABSORPTION MAXIMA AND 'CHARACTERISTIC'
WAVE-LENGTHS OF SOME ALKYL AND ARYL
ESTERS OF *d*-CAMPHOR- β -SULPHONIC
ACID IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

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The ultraviolet absorption spectra of methyl, ethyl, phenyl, tolyl (*o*- & *p*-) and naphthyl (α - & β -) esters of *d*-camphor- β -sulphonic acid have been determined in three solvents. The values of $\lambda_{\max}$ have been compared with those of the 'characteristic' wave-lengths (λ_c). There are marked discrepancies in the values of λ_c and $\lambda_{\max}$. An explanation for these differences is given.

Ultraviolet absorption spectra of methyl, ethyl, phenyl, tolyl (*o*- & *p*-) and naphthyl (α - & β -) esters of *d*-camphor- β -sulphonic acid have been reported in this communication.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The compounds mentioned above were prepared and purified according to methods described previously (Singh and Sarma, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 49). The absorption measurements were carried out in spectroscopically pure solvents (*viz.* methanol, ethanol and chloroform) with a Beckman DU ultraviolet spectrophotometer with a view to comparing the 'characteristic' wave-lengths (λ_c), deduced from Drude's one-term rotatory dispersion equation, with ultraviolet absorption maxima, $\lambda_{\max}$. The strength of the solutions was 0.50% in the case of methyl and ethyl esters, 0.005% in the case of α - and β -naphthyl esters and 0.10% in the case of *o*- and *p*-tolyl and phenyl esters, except 0.05% in the case of phenyl ester in methyl alcohol. The molecular extinction coefficients (ϵ) were calculated from the observed values of optical density. The peak values of the molecular extinction coefficients, $\epsilon_{\max}$, and the corresponding values of $\lambda_{\max}$ are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

<i>d</i> -Camphor- β -sulphonates.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.).	Solvent.	$\lambda_{\max}$.	$\epsilon_{\max}$.	λ_0^* .	$\lambda_0 - \lambda_{\max}$.
1. Methyl	0.50	MeOH	288 $m\mu$	25	320 $m\mu$	32
	"	EtOH	288	27	314	26
	"	CHCl ₃	288	28	320	32
2. Ethyl	0.50	MeOH	283	28	305	17
	"	EtOH	289	27	332	43
	"	CHCl ₃	287	30	292	3
3. Phenyl	0.05	MeOH	260	150	326	66
	0.10	EtOH	260	198	320	60
	"	CHCl ₃	285	1 to 2	307	35
	"		286	1 to 2		21
4. <i>o</i> -Tolyl	"	MeOH	263	322	316	53
	"	EtOH	263	347	318	55
	"	CHCl ₃	263	340	323	60
5. <i>p</i> -Tolyl	"	MeOH	265	326	312	47
	"	EtOH	265	333	325	60
	"	CHCl ₃	265	383	323	58
6. α -Naphthyl	0.005	MeOH	280	10726	316	36
	"	EtOH	280	10153	340	60
	"	CHCl ₃	280	7088	305	25
7. β -Naphthyl	"	MeOH	275	4847	311	36
	"	EtOH	275	5654	315	40
	"	CHCl ₃	275	3881	317	42

* Singh and Sarma, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 787. From Drude's equation.

DISCUSSION

The validity of Drude's rotatory dispersion equation,

$$[\alpha]_{\lambda} = \Sigma \frac{k}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2},$$

in which k represents the rotation constant and λ_0 , the 'characteristic' wave-length of the dominant absorption band governing rotation, has been tested by several workers. Lowry *et al.* (*Phil. Trans.*, 1927, 226A, 391; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1593) were interested to simply show that the rotatory dispersion equation curve could be represented by a very few terms, whereas Condon (*Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1937, 9, 432) regarded these terms as having average values resulting from the combination of several terms of more fundamental significance. Generally, the rotatory dispersion equation is expressed by one or two terms of Drude's formula, whereas the summation includes several terms of which the first one or two terms may be more important than the succeeding ones, which either are too small or may nearly cancel each other

and are therefore neglected. It is, thus, clear that this mode of representation by *one-* or *two-term* formula is far from reality. The terms found necessary in *one-* or *two-term* equation of Drude, within the limits of experimental error, thus, approximately represent the main contribution to the total optical activity. It is for these reasons that λ_0 , as determined from Drude's equation, differs from $\lambda_{\max}$. These differences may be large or small according to circumstances. In the present investigation, the differences between λ_0 and $\lambda_{\max}$ lie between 3 m μ for ethyl *d*-camphor- β -sulphonate in chloroform and 66 m μ for phenyl *d*-camphor- β -sulphonate in methyl alcohol. The λ_0 , deduced from Drude's *one-term* rotatory dispersion equation,

$$[\alpha]_{\lambda} = \frac{k}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2},$$

represents the wave-length of the dominant absorption band which governs the rotation. It should therefore be equal to one of the absorption bands ($\lambda_{\max}$) determined by direct absorption measurements. Again, in deducing λ_0 from rotatory dispersion measurements, we employ a very limited and short range of the spectrum from 670.8 m μ to 435.8 m μ , that is, 235 m μ . It is for this reason as well as those mentioned above, that there is discrepancy between the values of λ_0 and $\lambda_{\max}$.

The compounds recorded in Table I may be discussed as follows.

Methyl and Ethyl Esters of d-Camphor- β -sulphonic Acid.—The values of $\lambda_{\max}$ for these esters in three solvents are 288 and 289 m μ . They therefore represent the absorption band of the keto group in these compounds. The values of λ_0 (Table I) vary from 305 m μ to about 332 m μ except in the case of ethyl ester in chloroform where it is about 292 m μ . The differences ($\lambda_0 - \lambda_{\max}$) therefore range from 3 to 43 m μ .

Phenyl and Tolyl Esters of d-Camphor- β -sulphonic Acid.—In these esters there is a band at $\lambda_{\max}$ 260 to 265 m μ in the three solvents. There is, however, also a second band, $\lambda_{\max}$, in the case of phenyl ester at 285 m μ in ethyl alcohol and 286 m μ in chloroform. This belongs to the keto group. The value of λ_0 varies from about 307 to 326 m μ and thus differs from $\lambda_{\max}$ by 21 to 66 m μ (Table I).

Naphthyl Esters of d-Camphor- β -sulphonic Acid.—The value of $\lambda_{\max}$ in the case of α -naphthyl ester is 280 m μ , whereas in that of β -naphthyl ester it is 275 m μ in the three solvents. The ketonic band is associated with about 280 m μ , which is also the absorption maximum ($\lambda_{\max}$) of naphthyl radical. But the extinction coefficient, $\epsilon_{\max}$, of the keto group is much lower than that for the naphthyl radical. This band therefore appears to be due to both these groups. The values of the λ_0 s, (Table I) vary from 305 to 340 m μ . The difference, $\lambda_0 - \lambda_{\max}$, ranges between 25 and 60 m μ in the case of these esters.

It may be noted that these seven compounds exhibit rather simple ultraviolet absorption spectra. The alkyl esters exhibit only one band in the three solvents at $\lambda_{\max}$, 288 to 289 m μ . The phenyl ester exhibits one $\lambda_{\max}$ in three solvents at 260 m μ . It also shows a second band in ethyl alcohol and in chloroform at $\lambda_{\max}$ 285 to 286 m μ . The tolyl esters exhibit only a single band at 260-265 m μ . The naphthyl esters exhibit a band at 275 m μ (α -ester) and at 280 m μ (β -ester).

These values of λ_{max} , thus, are in several cases considerably different from those of λ_0 (Table I).

The authors reserve the study of other similar esters of camphor- β -sulphonic acids (*d* and *dl*).

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